

Nitration of 3-Bromo-4-iodonitrobenzene

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Dinitro-iodo compounds have received little attention as only a few of them are described in the literature. During a programme of research on nitration of some iodo compounds in this laboratory, nitration of 3-bromo-4-iodonitrobenzene was undertaken. Although it might yield a mixture of dinitro isomers, only 2-bromo-1-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene¹ could be isolated. It reacts with hydrazine hydrate to afford 2-bromo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine².

Nitration.—To a suspension of 3-bromo-4-iodonitrobenzene (10 g.) in H_2SO_4 (50 ml, d 1.82) fuming nitric acid (14 ml, d 1.5) was added dropwise with shaking. After heating on a water bath for an hour, the mixture was cooled and poured on crushed ice. The precipitate was crystallised successively from acetic acid, methanol, and ethanol to furnish 2-bromo-1-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene (7 g.) in yellow needles, m.p. 116°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample¹ of 2-bromo-1-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene remained undepressed. (Found: N, 7.39. Calc. for $C_6H_3O_4N_2Br$ I: N, 7.51%).

2-Bromo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine.—To a solution of 2-bromo-1-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene (1 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) 50% hydrazine hydrate (1.5 ml) was added. 2-Bromo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine was filtered after an hour. After crystallisation from ethanol, yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 172° (lit.² m.p. 172°), were obtained. (Found: Br., 29.19. Calc. for $C_6H_3O_4N_4Br$: Br, 28.85%).

The acetyl derivative, prepared by the usual method, crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 175-76°. (Found: Br, 25.29. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_5N_4Br$: Br, 25.04%).

The benzoyl derivative, prepared by the pyridine method, crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 198°. (Found: Br, 20.78. Calc. for $C_{12}H_9O_5N_4Br$: Br, 20.97%).

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1. Joshi and Deorha, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2414.

2. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 34.

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